

ON THE METHOD OF MATHEMATICAL INDUCTION IN CALCULATING INDEFINITE INTEGRALS AND TESTING NUMERICAL SERIES FOR CONVERGENCE

B.M. Mamadaliyev¹, M.M. Toxirova², Sh.A. Sodiqova³, S.Kh. Hazratqulova⁴

Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Kokand State University¹

Teacher, General Secondary School No. 55, Uzbekistan District, Fergana Region²

Student of Mathematics, Kokand State University³

Student of Mathematics, Kokand State University⁴

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20303980>

Abstract. This article studies the use of the method of mathematical induction in two important areas of mathematical analysis: testing numerical series for convergence and calculating repeated indefinite integrals. The induction method is valued for its simple logical structure and wide applicability in different branches of mathematics. First, the article recalls the general induction principle and the comparison theorem for positive series. Then the convergence of two numerical series is investigated through inequalities proved by mathematical induction. In the first example, the convergence of the factorial series is obtained by comparison with a geometric series. In the second example, the divergence of a series with a radical denominator is established by comparison with a generalized harmonic series. Finally, the article demonstrates how induction can be used to derive formulas for repeated indefinite integrals of exponential and trigonometric functions. The examples show that mathematical induction is an effective and rigorous method for proving formulas and solving problems in mathematical analysis.

Keywords: mathematical induction, numerical series, convergence, divergence, comparison test, generalized harmonic series, geometric series, indefinite integral, repeated integration, mathematical analysis.

Introduction

First of all, the method of mathematical induction is notable for its very simple and clear idea. Suppose that a certain hypothesis or statement $A(n)$ is formulated with the help of induction.

To prove that this hypothesis is true for every natural number n , the method of mathematical induction is applied as follows:

1. For $n = 1$, the truth of the statement $A(n)$ is verified.
2. It is assumed that, for $n = k$, the statement $A(n)$ is true.
3. The truth of the statement $A(n)$ for $n = k + 1$ is proved; in other words, the implication $A(k) \Rightarrow A(k + 1)$ is established.

After these three steps, it is concluded that the statement $A(n)$ is true for all natural numbers n .

The method of mathematical induction is widely and successfully used in many different, and sometimes very distant, areas of mathematics. In this article, we show the applications of this

method to testing numerical series for convergence and to calculating indefinite integrals by means of concrete examples.

A comparison theorem for positive series

It is known that, if the convergence or divergence of a positive series is known, then the convergence or divergence of another positive series whose terms are related to the terms of the first series can often be determined by comparison. Several theorems are connected with this idea. We recall one of them.

Theorem. Let $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n$ and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n$ be positive series. If, beginning with some value n_0 of n with $n_0 \geq 1$, the inequality

$$a_n \leq b_n$$

holds for all $n \geq n_0$, then the convergence of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n$$

implies the convergence of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n,$$

and the divergence of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n$$

implies the divergence of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n.$$

This theorem is one of the most convenient tools for applying mathematical induction to convergence problems, because the required comparison inequalities can often be proved by induction.

Example 1. Testing a factorial series for convergence

We test the following series for convergence:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n = \frac{1}{1!} + \frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{3!} + \dots + \frac{1}{n!} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!}.$$

For all $n \geq 1$, the following inequality holds:

$$A(n): \quad \frac{1}{n!} \leq \frac{1}{2^{n-1}}.$$

This inequality can be verified by the method of mathematical induction.

Proof.

1. For $n = 1$, we have

$$\frac{1}{1!} = \frac{1}{2^{1-1}},$$

so the statement is true.

2. Assume that, for $n = k$, the inequality is true, that is,

$$\frac{1}{k!} \leq \frac{1}{2^{k-1}}.$$

We prove the inequality for $n = k + 1$:

$$\frac{1}{(k+1)!} = \frac{1}{k!(k+1)} \leq \frac{1}{k!} \cdot \frac{1}{k+1} \leq \frac{1}{2^{k-1}} \cdot \frac{1}{k+1} \leq \frac{1}{2^{k-1}} \cdot \frac{1}{1+1} = \frac{1}{2^k}.$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{(k+1)!} \leq \frac{1}{2^k}.$$

Thus the inequality is true for all natural numbers n .

If we take

$$b_n = \frac{1}{2^{n-1}},$$

then

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{n-1}}$$

is a geometric series with ratio

$$q = \frac{1}{2} < 1,$$

and therefore it is convergent. Hence, by the comparison theorem, the given series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!}$$

is also convergent.

Example 2. Testing a series with radical denominators for convergence

Test the following series for convergence:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}}.$$

Using the method of mathematical induction, we can show that

$$A(n): \quad 1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} < 2\sqrt{n} \quad (n \neq 1).$$

We prove this inequality.

1. For $n = 1$, the inequality

$$1 < 2$$

is true.

2. Assume that, for $n = k$, the inequality

$$1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}} < 2\sqrt{k}$$

is true. We prove it for $n = k + 1$:

$$1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k+1}} < 2\sqrt{k} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k+1}}.$$

$$2\sqrt{k} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k+1}} = \frac{2\sqrt{k}\sqrt{k+1} + 1}{\sqrt{k+1}}.$$

$$\frac{2\sqrt{k}\sqrt{k+1} + 1}{\sqrt{k+1}} \leq \frac{k + (k+1) + 1}{\sqrt{k+1}} = 2\sqrt{k+1}.$$

Here we used the inequality

$$(\sqrt{k+1} - \sqrt{k})^2 = k + 1 - 2\sqrt{k}\sqrt{k+1} + k \geq 0.$$

Therefore,

$$1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k+1}} \leq 2\sqrt{k+1},$$

and the required inequality holds for all natural numbers n .

Now set

$$b_n = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

and

$$a_n = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{n}}.$$

From the proved inequality we obtain

$$a_n \leq b_n.$$

Consequently,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n.$$

Since

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2\sqrt{n}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{1/2}}$$

is a generalized harmonic series with exponent $p = \frac{1}{2} < 1$, it is divergent. Therefore, by the comparison theorem, the given series is also divergent.

Applications to indefinite integrals

We now give examples of applications of the method of mathematical induction to the calculation of indefinite integrals. In the formulas below, the notation $I_n(f)$ denotes the result of integrating the function $f(x)$ successively n times, that is,

$$I_n(f) = \int \int \dots \int f(x) dx,$$

where the integral sign is repeated n times.

Example 3. Repeated indefinite integrals of an exponential function

We prove the equality

$$A_n: \quad I_n(a^x) = \frac{1}{\ln^n(a)} a^x + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{c_i}{(n-i)!} x^{n-i},$$

where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are real constants.

Proof. We prove the equality using the method of mathematical induction.

1. For $n = 1$, we have

$$\int a^x dx = \frac{1}{\ln a} a^x + c_1,$$

so the statement is true.

2. Assume that, for $n = k$, the equality

$$I_k(a^x) = \frac{1}{\ln^k(a)} a^x + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k-i)!} x^{k-i}$$

is true. We show that it is true for $n = k + 1$:

By the definition of repeated integration and the induction hypothesis,

$$I_{k+1}(a^x) = \int \left(\frac{1}{\ln^k(a)} a^x + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k-i)!} x^{k-i} \right) dx.$$

$$I_{k+1}(a^x) = \frac{1}{\ln^{k+1}(a)} a^x + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k+1-i)!} x^{k+1-i} + c_{k+1}.$$

$$I_{k+1}(a^x) = \frac{1}{\ln^{k+1}(a)} a^x + \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} \frac{c_i}{(k+1-i)!} x^{k+1-i}.$$

Thus,

$$I_n(a^x) = \frac{1}{\ln^n(a)} a^x + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{c_i}{(n-i)!} x^{n-i}$$

for all natural numbers n .

Example 4. Repeated indefinite integrals of the sine function

We prove the equality

$$A_n: I_n(\sin x) = \sin\left(x + n \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{c_i}{(n-i)!} x^{n-i},$$

where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are real constants.

We prove this equality by the method of mathematical induction.

1. For $n = 1$, we have

$$\int \sin x \, dx = -\cos x + c_1 = \sin\left(x + \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + c_1,$$

which is true.

2. Assume that, for $n = k$, the equality

$$I_k(\sin x) = \sin\left(x + k \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k-i)!} x^{k-i}$$

is true. We verify it for $n = k + 1$:

By the definition of repeated integration and the induction hypothesis,

$$I_{k+1}(\sin x) = \int \left(\sin\left(x + k \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k-i)!} x^{k-i} \right) dx.$$

$$I_{k+1}(\sin x) = -\cos\left(x + k \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k-i)!} \cdot \frac{1}{k-i+1} x^{k-i+1} + c_{k+1}.$$

$$I_{k+1}(\sin x) = \sin\left(x + k \frac{3\pi}{2} + \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{(k+1-i)!} x^{k+1-i} + c_{k+1}.$$

$$I_{k+1}(\sin x) = \sin\left(x + (k+1) \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} \frac{c_i}{(k+1-i)!} x^{k+1-i}.$$

Therefore,

$$I_{k+1}(\sin x) = \sin\left(x + (k+1)\frac{3\pi}{2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} \frac{c_i}{(k+1-i)!} x^{k+1-i}$$

for all natural numbers n .

Such examples can be given in large numbers.

Conclusion

The examples considered above show that the method of mathematical induction is not only a theoretical proof technique but also a practical method for solving problems in mathematical analysis. In convergence problems, induction helps prove inequalities that make the comparison test applicable. In the calculation of repeated indefinite integrals, induction provides a rigorous way to establish general formulas from simple base cases. Therefore, the mathematical induction method is an effective and reliable tool for proving statements that depend on a natural-number parameter.

REFERENCES

1. Azlarov, T.; Mansurov, H. *Mathematical Analysis*. Tashkent, 1986.
2. Khudoyberganov, G.; Voriyev, A.; Mansurov, Kh.; Shoimqulov, B. *Lectures on Mathematical Analysis*. Tashkent, 2010.
3. Azlarov, T.; Mirakhmedov, M.; Otakoziyev, D.; Sobirov, M.; Tolaganov, S. *A Guide to Mathematics*. Part II. Tashkent, 1990.
4. Sadullayev, A.; Mansurov, H.; Khudoyberganov, G.; Vorisov, A.; Gulomov, R. *Mathematical ...* [the title is incomplete in the submitted manuscript].
5. Mamadaliyev, M. B.; Qodirova, M. Kh. "On the Concavity and Convexity of a Surface." *Scientific Bulletin of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute*, 2024, Issue 3, Pedagogy, UDC: 082.29.63, ORCID: 0009-0000-4127-8226.